

Isolation of Lupeol group of Triterpenes from *Dillenia indica* Linn. and *Diospyros perigrina*

T. SUNDARARAMAIAH*, S. K. RAMRAJ, K. LAKSHMAN RAO
and
(MRS.) V. VIMALABAI

Department of Chemistry, Nizam College,
Hyderabad-500001.

Manuscript received 7 January 1976; accepted 1 April 1976.

IN connection with our work on the reactions of triterpenes we needed large quantity of betulinic acid. The isolation of betulinic acid from the bark of *Dillenia indica*¹ and *Diospyros perigrina*² was reported. Since the other parts of *D. indica* were not examined earlier, we examined the fruit and heart-wood with a view that these parts of the plant also would yield betulinic acid.

The ether extracts of the powdered heart-wood and fruit of *D. indica* were fractionated into acidic (0.05%) and neutral (0.02%) fractions with 5% NaOH. The acidic fractions from both the parts were found to be identical (m.p. 298°–300°; $(\alpha)_D^{25} + 5^\circ$: crystallise from methanol as colourless needles) and identified as betulinic acid by comparison of the compound and its methyl ester (CH₂N₂: m.p. 220°–222°) with betulinic acid and methyl betulinate (TLC and IR). The neutral fraction from the wood was purified by chromatography over alumina and identified as β -sitosterol (m.p. 136°–37°; $(\alpha)_D^{25} - 36^\circ$) by comparison with authentic sample. The neutral fraction from the fruit (m.p. 250°–52°; $(\alpha)_D^{25} + 19^\circ$: crystallise from methanol as colourless needles) was identified as betulin by comparison of the compound and its diacetate (Ac₂O-pyridine: m.p. 220°) with betulin and betulin diacetate (TLC and IR).

The acidic fraction of the ether extract of the bark of *Diospyros perigrina* furnished the reported betulinic acid² in a yield of 3% and nothing was reported about the neutral fraction. In the present investigation the neutral fraction (0.03%) showed 2 spots on TLC. So it was absorbed over alumina column and eluted with benzene and benzene-chloroform (5:1). The benzene eluate furnished lupeol (m.p. 210°–12°; $(\alpha)_D^{25} + 24^\circ$: crystallise from methanol: compared with authentic sample). The benzene chloroform eluate gave betulin.

Acknowledgement

We thank Prof. M. M. Taquikhan, Head of the Chemistry Department, Nizam College, Hyderabad for providing facilities and U.G.C. for financial assistance. S.K.R. and K.L.R. thank V.V. Research Centre, Hyderabad for encouragement.

References

1. S. R. BHATTACHARJEE and A. CHATTERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 276.
2. L. RAMACHANDRA ROW, C. SANKARA RAO and T. SUNDARARAMAIAH, *Current Sci.*, 1964, 38, 367.

Studies on an Acid-Induced Cyclization Product of Ostruthin

A. K. BARUA, S. K. BANERJEE*, A. BASAK and P. K. BOSE
Bose Institute, Calcutta 9.

Manuscript received 14 February 1976, accepted 1 April 1976.

THE isolation of ostruthin (I) in a very high yield from the root and stem bark of *Atalantia missi-otis* Oliver was reported by us earlier¹. The present paper deals with the structure of an acid-induced cyclization product of ostruthin.

Ostruthin (I, 350 mg) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and then two drops of conc. H₂SO₄ was added. It was then heated on a steam bath for 15 min. On working up the product followed by purification by column chromatography over silica gel column a colourless crystalline compound, C₁₉H₂₂O₃, m.p. 175°–78° (M⁺ 298°), was obtained which was found to be homogeneous in TLC. The same product was also obtained on treatment of ostruthin with Ac₂O/H₂SO₄. Unlike Ostruthin it did not give any positive ferric chloride colour test. Its IR spectrum in Nujol mull showed a band at 1720 cm⁻¹ for the coumarinic lactone group but did not show any band for a free hydroxyl group and this indicated that the above product is most probably an acid-induced cyclization product (II).

The possible genesis of some of the important fragment ions in the mass spectrum of (II) is shown below.

The NMR spectrum of (II) (60 MHz, CDCl₃) showed sharp singlets at 0.92 δ and 1.05 δ for the six protons of two tertiary methyl groups ($\equiv$ C-CH₃). The sharp singlet at 1.26 δ (3H) is due to the tertiary methyl group attached to the carbon linked to the oxygen atom of the pyran ring. The signals at

* St. Xavier's College, Calcutta.

** The = OH in Fig. (I) to be treated as — OH.

2.63 δ (1H) and 2.77 δ (1H) were attributed to the two benzylic protons. The C-3 and C-4 protons of the coumarinic lactone ring appeared as doublet centered at 6.17 δ (1H, $J = 9.5$ Hz) and at 7.56 δ

(1H, $J = 9.5$ Hz). The C-8 and C-5 aromatic protons appeared as sharp singlets at 6.72 δ (1H) and 7.16 δ (1H) respectively. The six methylene and one methine protons appeared as broad multiplet centered at 1.62 δ . Thus the NMR data is fully in accord with the structure (II) proposed for the cyclized product.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Prof. S. M. Sircar, Ex-Director, Bose Institute, for his interest in this work. Thanks are due to Drs. K. G. Das and A.P.B. Sinha of the National Chemical Laboratory, Poona for the mass and NMR spectra. One of the authors (A.B.) is indebted to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

Reference

- 1 A. K. BABUA, S. K. BANERJEE, A. BASAK, S. CHAKRAVARTI, S. GHOSH, K. SETHI and P. K. BOSE, *Phytochem.*, 1974, 13, 2017.

Chemical Examination of the Leaves of *Careya arborea*

A. BASAK, S. K. BANERJEE*, MRS. L. BOSE** and K. BASU

BOSE INSTITUTE, CALCUTTA 9.

Manuscript received 16 February 1976; accepted 1 April 1976.

ISOLATION of a number of triterpenes have been reported earlier from the leaves of *Careya arborea*¹⁻⁴. The present communication reports the isolation of valoneic acid dilactone from the leaves

* St. Xavier's College, Calcutta.
** Rammohan College, Calcutta.

of the same plant. It was however isolated as its methylated derivative as the acid itself was found to be susceptible to aerial oxidation.

The ether insoluble part of the ethanolic extract of the leaves was hydrolysed with 5% ethanolic hydrochloric acid. The saponogenin thus obtained was extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with solvent ether for 24 hr. During this extraction a white solid precipitated out. It was filtered and found to be sparingly soluble in most common organic solvents, like benzene, ether, chloroform etc. and it turned dark on heating on a steam bath. So the material was suspended in a large volume of ethyl acetate and treated with ethereal diazomethane. On working up followed by purification by column chromatography a crystalline solid, C₂₈H₂₄O₁₃ (Ia, M⁺ 568), m.p. 258°-62° (dec.), $\lambda_{max}^{CHCl_3}$ 367, 352, 295 and 251 nm, was obtained. This was found to be homogeneous on TLC.

Its IR spectrum (CHCl₃) showed bands at 1745 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl) and 1730 cm⁻¹ (carbomethoxyl group). The bands at 1607 cm⁻¹ and 1575 cm⁻¹ were due to aromatic ring. Its mass spectral fragmentation pattern was commensurate with the structure (Ia).

It showed strong peaks at m/e 343, m/e 327, m/e 241 and m/e 225 all arising out of cleavage of the ether linkage. The intense peak at m/e 211 was due to the ion a.

The NMR spectrum of (Ia) (60 MHz, CDCl₃) showed sharp singlets at 3.80 δ (3H), 3.95 δ (6H), 4.05 δ (3H), 4.2 δ (3H) and 4.3 δ (3H) for the eighteen protons of the six methoxyl groups. The three protons of the carbomethoxyl group appeared as a singlet at 3.75 δ . The three aromatic protons at C-3 (ring A), C-3 (ring C) and at C-3 (ring B), appeared as singlets at 7.2 δ (1H), 7.3 δ (1H) and 7.65 δ (1H), respectively. The downfieldship of the proton at C-3 (ring B) is most probably due to the proximity of the lactone carbonyl on one hand and the oxygen of the ether linkage on the other hand.

The methylated product on saponification furnished an acid which was crystallized from methanol, C₂₇H₂₂O₁₃ (Ib, M⁺ 554), m.p. 273°-76°. Its IR spectrum (Nujol mull) showed bands at 1745 cm⁻¹ (lactone carbonyl), 1712 cm⁻¹ (carboxyl group), 1607 cm⁻¹ and 1575 cm⁻¹ (aromatic rings). The acid (Ib) on ethylation with ethereal diazoethane furnished (Ic), C₂₉H₂₆O₁₃, m.p. 290-94° (dec.). Its NMR spectrum (60 MHz, pyridine) showed sharp singlets at 3.92 δ (3H), 3.95 δ (6H), 4.05 δ (3H), 4.22 δ